

1 Publication patterns in the humanities: an author-level 2 analysis of generational shifts and changing research 3 agendas

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13 14 **Abstract**

15 The humanities have distinct publication practices compared to the sciences, with books
16 and local language literature being essential. This study aims to identify and analyze the
17 publication patterns of humanities scholars in Spanish-speaking countries, revealing
18 unique publication behaviors and fostering diverse perspectives rather than linear
19 knowledge progression. We analyzed the publication histories of approximately 40,000
20 scholars from 1950 to 2021 using data from the Dialnet database. By identifying
21 archetypal publication profiles, we explored their distribution across generational cohorts
22 and research topics. Our findings reveal substantial generational shifts towards journal-
23 centric publication patterns probably influenced by bibliometric-driven evaluation
24 systems. They also show a relation between publication patterns and research topics.
25 This highlights the need for more inclusive assessment practices that recognize the
26 diverse nature of humanities scholarship. We contribute to ongoing discussions on
27 promoting bibliodiversity in research assessment and the potential impacts of current
28 policies on the humanities.

29 30 **Keywords**

31 humanities, publication patterns, bibliodiversity, research evaluation, Spanish-speaking
32 countries, generational shifts

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48 The humanities are distinct from other sciences. Unlike other disciplines, books remain
49 an essential format of scientific publishing (Giménez-Toledo et al. 2017; Engels et al.
50 2018; Zuccala and Robinson-García 2019), and their target audience is often more
51 scattered and diverse (Hammarfelt 2016; Sivertsen 2016) with non-English literature
52 playing an important role in its dissemination (Kulczycki et al. 2020). Citation patterns
53 differ as well (Wang 2013): older works are more likely to still be cited (Hammarfelt 2016),
54 and research primarily involves exploring new perspectives and fostering the
55 coexistence of competing knowledge rather than following a linear process of
56 development characterized by big breakthroughs (Ochsner et al. 2013). Furthermore,
57 solo research is still common (Nederhof 2006). These disciplinary specificities have led
58 to the emergence of diverse valuation regimes—that is, differing logics, practices and
59 standards by which research quality and relevance are judged (Reale et al. 2018;
60 Robinson-Garcia et al. 2023). As a result, research evaluation remains a highly
61 controversial issue (Hammarfelt 2017; Toledo 2020). This lack of consensus is related to
62 the social structure of these fields, generally organized around schools of thought or
63 ‘tribes’ (Becher and Trowler 2001) which compete, contrasting with the ‘paradigmatic’
64 organization of the Natural and Exact Sciences (Kuhn 1996). These differences have
65 sometimes been interpreted as weakness of humanities (Sokal 1996; Linmans 2009),
66 rather than merely different research styles.

67

68 Given the particularities of the humanities, a body of literature has been built within the
69 fields of scientometrics and research evaluation over the last twenty years trying to better
70 understand its dynamics (Verleysen and Weeren 2016). For this, studies have focused
71 mainly on three issues: differences on publication patterns, database coverage
72 limitations (Hicks 1999; Archambault et al. 2006; Sivertsen and Larsen 2012; Glänzel et
73 al. 2016), and the validity of citations as a proxy for impact or quality (Hug et al. 2013;
74 Ochsner et al. 2013) proposing a range of alternative indicators (Torres-Salinas and
75 Moed 2009; Hammarfelt 2014; Zuccala and Robinson-García 2019).

76

77 This study is framed within the first stream of literature, that is, the understanding of
78 publication patterns within the Humanities. Our goal is to identify types of humanists
79 based on their publication patterns and understand the factors underlying the differences
80 between these types. We want to understand to what extent humanists tend to publish
81 in a diverse range of outlets. Is it common to all fields? How is a journal-centric evaluation
82 culture affecting their publishing habits (Hammarfelt and de Rijcke 2015)? What is the
83 role played by language (Leeuwen 2013), database indexing (Ossenblok et al. 2012;
84 López Piñero and Hicks 2015; Kulczycki et al. 2018), scope (Chavarro et al. 2014;
85 Kulczycki and Korytkowski 2020) or research topic (López Piñero and Hicks 2015;
86 Ràfols et al. 2019; Kulczycki and Korytkowski 2020)?

87

88 To this aim, we analyze publication patterns of individual scholars during their complete
89 academic career. We examine the publication history of 39,753 scholars from Spanish
90 speaking countries who started publishing from 1950 onwards up to 2021. We consider
91 around 1.2 million publications in all outlets and languages, studying 13 different fields
92 from the humanities. Our dataset is extracted from Dialnet¹, a specialized bibliographic
93 database focused on the social sciences and humanities, maintained by the Dialnet
94 Foundation in collaboration with over 80 Spanish and Latin American universities and
95 public institutions (Mateo 2015; Arroyo-Machado and Robinson-Garcia 2023). Dialnet

96 indexes diverse publication types with a strong focus on Spanish-language outputs,
97 aiming to reflect national and regional scholarly production in the Spanish-speaking world
98 often overlooked by international citation indexes. The uniqueness of this data lies not
99 only on the richness of publication types and languages, but also by the fact that author
100 profiles are manually curated and regularly updated by Spanish university, public and
101 special libraries related to the Dialnet Foundation through a consortium agreement. This
102 allows us to track their complete publication history, identify their starting publishing date,
103 compute their career length or differentiate between outputs indexed and non-indexed
104 publications in mainstream bibliometric databases (i.e., Scopus and Web of Science).

105

106 Based on this dataset, we built eight variables for each scholar, defining their publication
107 patterns by publication type, language, and database indexing. We then computed an
108 archetypal analysis (Eugster and Leisch 2009) per discipline. This allows us to identify
109 extreme-type configurations of humanists based on their publication patterns. A
110 hierarchical clustering analysis allowed us to group archetypes across fields, identifying
111 six distinct publication profiles in the humanities. We then computed distance measures
112 between each scholar and archetype to measure their resemblance to them.
113 Furthermore, we assigned scholars to their most similar archetype and explored
114 differences between archetypes in terms of generational cohort (that is, the year when
115 they first started publishing), and research topic. Topics were identified by applying the
116 Leiden community detection algorithm (Traag et al. 2019) to a co-occurrence network
117 based on keywords extracted from publication titles. Then, we computed the Jaccard
118 distance between archetypes across fields in order to identify differences in the topics
119 studied by humanists based on their publication profiles. Further details are provided in
120 the Data and Methods section.

121

122 We contribute to current literature in several ways. First, we analyze publication patterns
123 at the author level, revealing the extent of variation and contributing to the debate on the
124 diverse literatures within the humanities (Hicks 2005; Nederhof 2006). These patterns
125 may not be only disciplinary but also generational, as the rise of bibliometric-driven
126 evaluation systems and the “Publish or Perish” culture has incentivized shifts in what,
127 how, and where humanists publish (Cañibano et al. 2018; Knöchelmann 2024). Second,
128 we offer novel insights into current research policy discussions on promoting
129 bibliodiversity in research assessment and the potential risks of policies that alter
130 publication habits (Hammarfelt and de Rijcke 2015; CoARA 2022). Finally, we examine
131 the relationship between research topics, language and geographic outreach —an
132 under-researched issue often mentioned to resist changes in publication patterns within
133 the humanities (Kulczycki et al. 2020; Kulczycki and Korytkowski 2020).

134

135 **Results**

136 **Distribution of scholars by field and general publication trends**

137 We explore the publication patterns of 39,753 humanists distributed among 13 research
138 fields (**Fig. 1**). Historians, philologists, and philosophers represent half of the population
139 (50.2%), whereas Geography, Paleontology and Cultural Studies account for less than
140 5% of the population (**a**). This distribution is modified slightly when looking at productivity
141 differences among fields (**b**). The proportion of outputs from the three largest fields
142 increases slightly to 52.7%, with History representing more than a quarter of the

143 publications (26.8%), that is 4.3% higher than expected. Literature also produced more
 144 publications than expected compared to other fields, with a difference of 3.0 points.
 145 Conversely, Philosophy constitutes 12.4% of the workforce but accounts for only 10.2%
 146 of all publications.

147
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Fig. 1 Descriptives of population of scholars and outputs by field.

149
 150

151 The distribution of career lengths and first publication years of scholars across fields
 152 reveals significant variations. In terms of career length (c), Literature and Geography
 153 stand out with the highest mean values (21.7 and 21.2 respectively), indicating the
 154 presence of more senior scholars in these fields. By contrast, scholars from fields such
 155 as Translation Studies, Anthropology, and Music have shorter career lengths on average,
 156 indicating a younger academic workforce. Regarding generational differences (d), most
 157 scholars began their academic career during the 1990s and 2000s; however notable
 158 differences exist across fields. Translation Studies and Anthropology show the most
 159 recent mean entry points into academia, with means around 2003 and 2002, and
 160 medians both in 2005. On the other hand, Literature and Geography have the oldest
 161 mean first publication years, around 1995, indicating a more established cohort of
 162 scholars.

163

164 Regarding publication patterns (e), articles are the predominant publication type across
 165 most fields, particularly in Paleontology (79.2%) and Music (78.1%). Philosophy also
 166 shows a high proportion of articles (62.0%). In contrast, fields like Philology and History,
 167 while still favoring articles (47.4 and 49.7%, respectively), show a larger presence of
 168 book chapters (31.6 and 31.4% respectively). The prevalence of books is particularly
 169 notable in Literature (16.8%) and Philosophy (11.7%). Fields like Anthropology and
 170 Archaeology exhibit a balanced distribution between articles and chapters, with
 171 Translation Studies showing 46.8% articles and 31.3% chapters, Philology with 47.4%
 172 articles and 31.6% chapters, and Geography with 46.6% of articles and 29.8% of

173 chapters. In terms of publication language (f), Spanish is the dominant language in most
174 fields. It accounts for 89.8% of publications in Literature, 82.6% in Cultural Studies and
175 79.9% in Philosophy. In contrast, Paleontology stands out with a significant proportion of
176 outputs in English language publications (44.5%). English also plays a notable role in
177 fields like Translation Studies (30.0%) and Philology (20.8%). Other languages such as
178 Catalan, French and Portuguese are also present but to a lesser extent. Catalan is
179 particularly present in Philology (9.2%) and Geography (7.6%).
180

181 **Humanists' publication profiles**

182 For each scholar, we defined eight variables to describe their publication patterns to
183 better understand their preferred outlets. Six of these variables relate to publication
184 types: four relate to authored publications (journal articles, books, chapters and
185 proceedings), and two with edited publications (edited conference proceedings and
186 edited books). The other two variables relate to the geographic scope of the output. One
187 relates to the number of non-English publications and the second to the number of
188 publications indexed in mainstream international scientific databases (i.e., Scopus and
189 Web of Science). Further details on the data processing and methodological design are
190 provided in the Data and Methods section.
191

192 Using these variables, we applied an archetypal analysis to identify the types of
193 publication profiles exhibited by humanists. Archetypal analysis (Cutler and Breiman
194 1994; Eugster and Leisch 2009) is a methodology used to identify extreme points in a
195 multidimensional dataset that best represent the diversity of the data. Unlike traditional
196 clustering methods, which group similar data points into clusters, this method identifies
197 extreme examples within the data, providing a convex hull that encompasses the
198 dataset. Furthermore, it provides a similarity measure, called the α -score, which
199 indicates how similar each case is to the identified archetypes. The number of archetypes
200 is defined by following an elbow criterion after plotting the screeplot of a residual sum of
201 squares (RSS) analysis (**Appendix, Fig. A1-14**). Hence, the number of archetypes
202 identified varies per discipline, with 8 disciplines exhibiting three different archetypes and
203 5 disciplines exhibiting 2. In order to identify similarities across fields, we conducted a
204 hierarchical clustering analysis of all archetype-discipline combinations. In this way, we
205 are able to identify commonalities and differences of profiles across and within
206 disciplines.
207

208 Overall, we have identified six profiles which are spread across the humanities. **Fig. 2A**
209 displays a heatmap showing the normalized values of the eight publication variables
210 used to define each archetype. Archetypes are sorted and grouped based on hierarchical
211 clustering. The corresponding fields and archetype numbers are shown on the right side
212 of the y-axis. To enhance readability and engagement, we gave each cluster of
213 archetypes or profile, a descriptive name that reflects its core characteristics. **Fig. 2B**
214 shows the distance between these profiles, displaying how they cluster together based
215 on their publication patterns. These are the following: the bridger, the cosmopolitan, the
216 local chronicler, the sage, the polymath and the participant. By naming these profiles, we
217 aim to provide a clearer understanding of the diverse publication practices in the
218 humanities and highlight the generational and cultural shifts influencing these patterns.
219 **Table 1** provides a summary of the main features characterizing each archetype.

220 **Fig. 2. Clustering and spatial distribution of archetypes in the humanities: (a)**
 221 **Hierarchical clustering and heatmap based on publication profiles, (b) MDS visual**
 222 **representation of disciplines and archetypes reflecting their relational distances.**

223 The most widespread profiles are those of the participants and the local chroniclers,
 224 which are both present across 11 of the 13 disciplines analyzed. In the case of the
 225 participants, the two fields in which they are absent are Language & Linguistics, and
 226 Literature. This profile is characterized by publishing in national languages mainly. We
 227 name them participants as they tend to participate in collaborative works with book
 228 chapters as their preferred publication venue. However, researchers exhibiting a
 229 participant publication profile will occasionally use any of the other publication venues
 230 analyzed, except for journal articles indexed in Web of Science or Scopus. In the case
 231 of the local chroniclers, these are present in all disciplines except for Language &
 232 Linguistics, and Paleontology. They are characterized by publishing mainly journal
 233 articles in national language (i.e., non-English), and only occasionally books or in
 234 indexed journals.

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 238

Table 1. Summary of the six archetypes identified

Archetype	Main publication formats	Language / Indexing profile	Disciplines
Participant	Mainly book chapters	Mostly national-language outputs; low reliance on indexed journals	All except for Language & Linguistics; Literature
Local chronicler	Primarily journal articles; occasional books/chapters	Almost entirely non-English; rarely indexed in Scopus/WoS	All except for Language & Linguistics; Paleontology
Cosmopolitan	Dominated by journal articles	Higher share of English and indexed publications	Philology, History, Archaeology, Arts, Translation Studies, Anthropology, Philosophy
Bridger	Mainly journal articles	Mixed: national-language + English; both indexed and non-indexed journals	Language & Linguistics; Paleontology
Polymath	Wide mix: books, chapters, articles, proceedings	Mostly non-English; non-indexed outlets	Language & Linguistics; Literature
Sage	Mainly monographs; occasional articles	Predominantly national-language	Literature only

239

240 The third most common profile is that of the cosmopolitans. Named like that due to the
241 high proportion of publications which are placed as articles in mainstream journals.
242 Cosmopolitans are present in 7 disciplines, these are: Philology, History, Archaeology,
243 Arts, Translation Studies, Anthropology and Philosophy. Next, we observe two
244 publication profiles which are only present in two disciplines respectively. These are the
245 bridgers and the polymaths. Bridgers are scholars who primarily publish journal articles,
246 engaging with both national and mainstream communities by publishing in both, in
247 national and English languages, as well as in indexed and non-indexed journals. These
248 scholars are present in the disciplines of Language & Linguistics, and Paleontology. On
249 the other hand, polymaths tend to use a wide variety of publication venues, similarly to
250 the profile of the participants, although with a lesser emphasis on book chapters. And
251 again, they publish in non-English languages and in non-mainstream journals. These
252 scholars are present in Language & Linguistics, and Literature. Finally, we observe one
253 profile which is distinctive of just one of the disciplines in the Humanities, that is the sage,
254 which is only present in Literature. These scholars are characterized by publishing mainly
255 monographs in national language, although occasionally also publishing journal articles.
256

257 Overall, we observe how publication choices are varied within the humanities, with
258 different publication patterns observed within and across fields. While many similarities
259 exist among some of the identified profiles, others are unique to specific disciplines,
260 reflecting the richness and diversity of publication habits.
261

262 **Generational differences on publication patterns by field**

263 Next, we hypothesize the existence of different profiles within disciplines as a reflection
264 of a generational shift, where publication patterns respond to the context in which they
265 are produced. Phenomena such as bibliometric-driven evaluation systems, a “Publish or
266 Perish” culture, and a generation of digitally native scholars who may prioritize novelty
267 and shorter communication formats over longer, more reflective works, could be driving
268 these differences across cohorts.
269

270 We explore this in **Fig. 3**, which plots the share of scholars by publication profile across
271 disciplines over time. The x-axis represents scholars’ first publication year which is used
272 as a proxy for their generational cohort, ranging from 1960 to 2020. The data reveals
273 that generational shifts are taking place both, in terms of dominant archetypes within
274 disciplines, and the emergence of new publication profiles. Similarities can be found in
275 the fields of History, Anthropology, Archaeology and the Arts, dominated by the local
276 chronicler and the participant profiles, but with an incipient growth of the cosmopolitan
277 profile among younger scholars. Meanwhile, the other two profiles, the participant and
278 the local chronicler, remain cross-generational, suggesting a more stable presence in
279 these fields across different cohorts. A similar trend is observed in Philology and
280 Philosophy, where the cosmopolitan profile has become more prominent among newer
281 generations. However, these show that the local chronicler profile is adopted by older
282 scholars, with a marked decline especially in Philology since the late 1990s, indicating a
283 shift from publishing in collective monographs.
284

285
286

287 **Fig. 3 Generational shifts in publication profiles across disciplines.**

288
289

290 In Cultural Studies and Geography, we observe a co-existence between the participant
 291 profile, characterized by publishing mainly book chapters, and the local chronicler, which
 292 prioritizes journal articles in national language. In the case of Geography, we observe a
 293 U shape in the distribution of participants, whereas in Cultural Studies, there is an even
 294 split which oscillates over the study period. But there is no dominant pattern across fields,
 295 reflecting the richness and diversity of the humanities in terms of publication patterns. In
 296 the case of Music, for instance, the pattern is somewhat the reverse, with the local
 297 chronicler being a cross-generational profile and the participant profile being adopted by
 298 generations from the 1990s and 2000s, although declining in the case of younger
 299 generations.

300

301 Paleontology is a unique case, showing distinct patterns compared to other disciplines.
 302 Here the bridger—who combines publishing in national language with mainstream
 303 journals—, is the dominant profile, with a smaller share of participant profiles are present
 304 across multiple generations. Other distinct cases include Language & Linguistics, and
 305 Literature. In the case of the former, two profiles are present: the polymath, who tends to

306 use a diversity of publication venues and formats, and the bridgers. Scholars showcasing
 307 the polymath profile are cross-generational, while there is a clear rise of scholars with a
 308 bridger profile among recent generations, pointing towards an effort to reach wider and
 309 more international audiences. Finally, Literature is the only discipline exhibiting the sage
 310 profile, characterized by scholars who primarily publish books. However, this profile is
 311 associated with older generations of scholars. In contrast, newer generations in the field
 312 tend to exhibit a polymath and a local chronicler profile, suggesting a shift in terms of
 313 publication practices. The dominance of the local chronicler profile still suggests the
 314 importance of national-language journals within the field over mainstream journals.

315

316 **Fig. 4 Thematic landscape and comparison of research portfolios by archetype in**
 317 **History, Philology, Philosophy and Arts., which represent the four largest fields in**
 318 **our dataset.**

319

320

321 **The relation between research topics and publication patterns**

322 Next, we explore whether publication profiles are associated with broad tendencies in
 323 topic engagement. Since archetypes are derived from patterns in publication, comparing
 324 their thematic focus allows us to assess how these publication behaviors relate to
 325 research topics. We translated non-English titles into English and extracted keywords
 326 using the ChatGPT API (OpenAI 2022). We then applied the Leiden community detection
 327 algorithm (Traag et al. 2019) to group keywords into clusters or topics. We identified a
 328 total of 1,437 topics (see Supplementary material to read the list of topics) which were
 329 clustered into eight major areas. Based on these topics, we created a vector for each
 330 archetype-discipline combination, representing the distribution of records among topics.
 331 A detailed description of the methodological approach followed is provided in the Data
 332 and Methods section.

333

334 **Fig. 4** shows the resulting thematic landscape for the complete dataset along with
 335 overlaid maps of different archetypes and fields as illustrative examples. The top-left
 336 of **Fig. 4** shows the thematic landscape for all fields, with numbered nodes representing
 337 topics, their size indicating the number of publications within each topic and colors
 338 depicting major areas. The largest topics are Philosophical Approaches to Cultural
 339 Studies (node 33, 43,749 publications), followed by Historiographical Evolution in
 340 Spanish-Speaking Contexts (node 42, 43,474 publications) and Teaching and Learning
 341 Strategies in Second Language Acquisition (node 67, 35,199 publications). Topics are
 342 linked based on the co-occurrence of keywords across topics. The right side of **Fig. 4**
 343 showcases the overlaid maps for the archetypes identified in the fields of History,
 344 Philology, Philosophy and Arts, which are the four largest fields in the dataset. Overall,
 345 we observe how different fields will concentrate their publications in different major areas.
 346 For instance, in the case of History, we observe a larger concentration within the area of
 347 Spanish and Latin American History, while in Philology, most of the publications revolve
 348 around the area of Translation and Linguistic Studies. A visual inspection of the map
 349 within fields does not reveal clear differences across publication profiles. For instance,
 350 archetypes in Philosophy seem quite similar in terms of topic distribution. However, in
 351 the case of the cosmopolitan profile in Arts or Philology, we do see some differences with
 352 the other two profiles.
 353

354 **Fig. 5 Thematic similarity of profiles across academic fields: (a) MDS**
 355 **representation based on thematic similarity, (b) same representation, faceted by**
 356 **academic field.**

357 While the number of topics within each discipline is large and detailed interpretation of
 358 individual topics is not always feasible, our goal here is to assess whether archetypes
 359 tend to be thematically closer or more distinct within each field. Rather than mapping
 360 profiles to specific topics, we focus on identifying patterns of thematic proximity or
 361 divergence between publication profiles using structured similarity measures.
 362
 363
 364

365 In **Fig. 5** we look systematically into such differences. For this, we vectorize the
366 distribution of topics among archetype-discipline combinations and compute within each
367 discipline, the similarity between thematic profiles using the Jaccard distance. The
368 distances are available in **Table A1**. In this way, we assess the extent to which scholars
369 associated with different archetypes share common research topics. To visualize such
370 distance, we apply Multidimensional Scaling (MDS) with a two-dimensional solution (see
371 the Data and Methods section). **Fig. 5A** shows the general topic similarity for each profile
372 and their respective fields. As observed, different profiles within the same field will be
373 close to each other relative to the other fields as expected. Fields will be closer or more
374 distant depending on their thematic similarity, for instance, Arts is close to History, linking
375 through History of Arts while Cultural Studies is closer to Anthropology, History, Arts and
376 Philosophy.

377
378 **Fig. 5B** shows an overlay for the distinct fields in order to analyze difference within field.
379 As observed, clear thematic distinctions emerge between publication profiles. Scholars
380 exhibiting cosmopolitan profile tend to publish on topics that are distinctly different from
381 those associated with other profiles. In contrast, when the local chronicler and participant
382 profiles coexist, they generally engage with similar research topics. The polymath profile
383 clearly distinguishes itself thematically from the bridger in the case of Language &
384 Linguistics but shows greater thematic similarity with the local chronicler in the case of
385 Literature, where the sage shows a more distinct profile. Again, the same kind of
386 distinction can be observed in the case of the bridger, which remains thematically distinct
387 from the participant in Paleontology, but shows a greater thematic distance with the
388 polymath in Language & Linguistics. In all, this shows a link between publication patterns
389 and research topics.

390

391 **Discussion**

392 Research evaluation systems have historically mistreated the humanities (Linmans
393 2009), often pushing them to adopt the same publication patterns as the sciences and
394 other fields (Ossenblok et al. 2012; López Piñero and Hicks 2015). This trend has
395 persisted despite widespread recognition that the humanities exhibit distinct publication
396 behaviors driven by their unique audiences and communication goals (Nederhof 2006).
397 Our analysis of publication patterns across humanists' publication histories may reflect
398 such pressure as well as the coexistence of different profiles of scholars. Through the
399 examination of a large dataset covering the publication history of nearly 40,000 scholars
400 across 13 fields within the humanities, we can identify and point to factors affecting these
401 differences in the choice of publication outlets by humanists.

402

403 The humanities have traditionally been portrayed as exhibiting a broad spectrum of
404 publication patterns across fields and specialties (Frandsen and Nicolaisen 2008). In
405 fact, different studies have highlighted the distinction between journal-based and book-
406 based disciplines (Hammarfelt 2016; Kulczycki et al. 2018). A key insight from our study
407 is that there is heterogeneity in publication patterns within the humanities with notable
408 differences across disciplines. This challenges the reasoning behind aggregating them
409 and treating them uniformly in most studies. We observe six publication profiles, —the
410 bridger, the cosmopolitan, the local chronicler, the sage, the polymath and the
411 participant—, each of them representing different preferences in terms of publication

412 patterns. The participant and local chronicler profiles are widely spread, as they are
413 common in 11 of the 13 disciplines analyzed. The cosmopolitan profile is present in more
414 than half of the disciplines. The remaining profiles seem to be more field-specific with the
415 sage profile as the one that is only observed in Literature.

416
417 Our findings highlight distinct generational transitions in publication practices across
418 disciplines. Examples of such changes are the emergence of younger scholars who favor
419 publishing in international journals in English language (cosmopolitan profile) in fields
420 such as History or Philology, while abandoning more traditional forms of publications
421 such as monographs and books in Literature (the sage profile). These shifts go in
422 different directions and vary in prominence by discipline. For instance, in the case of
423 Music, there is a vast majority of scholars showing a preference for publishing in journal
424 articles, although we observe an increase of scholars who started publishing in the late
425 1990s and 2000s who favor journal articles (participant profile). Hence, differences are
426 not homogeneous across the humanities. In fields such as Anthropology, Archaeology,
427 and Arts, there is a co-existence between the local chronicler and the participant, with
428 the cosmopolitan publication profile rising among younger scholars, which indicates a
429 strong orientation toward publishing in indexed journals and engaging in international
430 discourse. These examples and many others suggest how different fields are confronting
431 a changing publishing and academic landscape in which internationalization and
432 mainstream publishing are becoming more important for younger generations, while
433 traditional publication outlets continue to play a significant role for scholars across
434 cohorts in many disciplines.

435
436 As our analysis is based on data from a particular national and linguistic context, we
437 acknowledge that some of these patterns may not generalize to other countries or
438 language communities, especially given the known variability across the humanities.
439 Moreover, changes over time in publication patterns could partly reflect evolving
440 database coverage in Scopus and Web of Science indexing rather than shifts in author
441 preferences alone. These limitations should be considered when interpreting our
442 findings.

443
444 The identification of these publication profiles—and their varying presence across
445 disciplines and generations—demonstrates that no single publication model dominates
446 the humanities. This diversity reflects different epistemic cultures, audiences, and
447 research goals, and helps explain why uniform evaluation systems often fail to capture
448 the full spectrum of scholarly contributions. Our results also show that generational shifts
449 are occurring in several fields, with younger scholars more likely to adopt internationally
450 oriented and journal-based publication strategies. This tendency may partly reflect
451 pressures from evaluation systems that have tended to prioritize publication in
452 international journals and in outlets of high relevance as measured by citation-based
453 metrics, as a means to increase research visibility and alignment with global standards
454 (Jiménez-Contreras et al. 2003; Buela-Casal 2007). However, such an approach runs
455 counter to more recent recommendations, which advocate for research assessment
456 practices that also recognize local relevance and contextual diversity (Hicks et al. 2015).
457 These changes are not necessarily problematic in themselves, but they raise concerns
458 when driven more by external evaluation pressures than by scholarly fit or epistemic
459 need. Hence, the diversity we observe supports the case for more inclusive and flexible

460 evaluation frameworks, particularly those that can recognize both emerging and
461 traditional forms of scholarly output.

462

463 The preference for publishing venues is, in many cases, determined by the research
464 topic, pointing towards a linkage with the potential audience addressed by humanists
465 (Nederhof 2006). This is especially noticeable with profiles which show a preference for
466 publication in English language or in journals indexed in Web of Science or Scopus,
467 demonstrating that policies oriented towards these publications may contribute to biases
468 in the production of knowledge towards topics which may not reflect national interests
469 (Hicks et al. 2015; López Piñeiro and Hicks 2015).

470

471 Our study underscores the ongoing challenges in achieving bibliodiversity within the
472 humanities. Not only does it confirm the recognized importance of books and publications
473 in the national language but shows how these publication patterns are evolving;
474 highlighting the importance of introducing policies that maintain such bibliodiversity in
475 order to foster a rich and varied topic portfolio in these fields. Our analysis of publication
476 patterns in the humanities reveals significant generational shifts and the influence of
477 research evaluation policies on shaping academic behavior. The findings suggest an
478 unequal move towards journal-centric publication practices among newer generations,
479 driven by the pressures of current evaluation systems (López Piñeiro and Hicks 2015).
480 To foster a truly diverse and inclusive research environment, developing evaluation
481 frameworks that recognize the full spectrum of scholarly contributions in the humanities
482 is imperative. Further research is needed to explore the long-term implications of these
483 trends on the development of knowledge and the sustainability of diverse research
484 agendas in the humanities.

485

486 **Data and methods**

487 **Data collection and processing**

488 We used data from Dialnet, a bibliographic database which indexes social sciences and
489 humanities literature from Spanish-speaking countries since 2001. The Dialnet
490 Foundation provided data encompassing 825,604 publication records from 60,063
491 authors in the humanities. These data were shared directly by the Foundation in several
492 structured files, free of charge and under a confidentiality agreement, specifically for this
493 research project. Our analysis focused on publications from 1950 to 2021, which
494 narrowed the dataset to 806,378 publications and 57,742 researchers across 17 distinct
495 disciplines. To standardize field sizes, some fields were consolidated, resulting in a total
496 of 13 fields. Details of these fields are provided in **Table A2** in the Appendix. Additionally,
497 we included only scholars with at least two papers, reducing the final count to 39,753
498 scholars.

499

500 Researchers' career length was calculated as the difference between the years of their
501 first and last publications. Also, we use scholars' first publication year as a proxy for their
502 generational cohort. This is not intended as a sociological definition of "generation," but
503 as an operational indicator that captures temporal differences in entry into academic
504 publishing. We recognize this has implications on the results, since an academic career
505 may start long before the researcher publishes their research and may end long after
506 they publish their last publication. Moreover, some of their publications may not be

507 indexed in Dialnet. We then categorized their outputs into six types: books, book
508 chapters, articles, conference proceedings articles, edited books, and edited
509 proceedings. Additionally, we examine the outreach of their outlets using two variables:
510 indexing in mainstream databases, specifically Web of Science or Scopus; and
511 publication language, distinguishing between English and non-English publications. It is
512 important to consider that, in principle, these two variables are not mutually exclusive.

513

514 All data processing tasks were conducted using Python (v. 3.11.5). Descriptives,
515 statistical analyses and visualizations were conducted in the R statistical computing
516 language (v. 4.2.2) (R Core Team 2021). Thematic landscapes were generated using the
517 visualization software VOSviewer (Van Eck and Waltman 2010). Data underlying this
518 study and supplementary materials are available at Zenodo². Code scripts are available
519 at the GitHub repository³.

520

521 **Archetypal analysis**

522 In this paper, we have implemented an archetypal analysis. Archetypal analysis does not
523 aim at classifying observations into distinct groups but rather represents each
524 observation as a convex combination of a few extreme points, known as archetypes.
525 This means that observations are not clustered into discrete types; instead, each
526 observation is positioned in relation to all archetypes, with a weighting that reflects its
527 distance to each of them. These archetypes can be seen as distinct extreme types,
528 capturing distinct and extreme patterns of scholarly behavior within the dataset. Given
529 an $n \times m$ matrix X representing a multivariate data set with n observations and m
530 attributes, the archetypal analysis finds the matrix Z of k m –dimensional archetypes by
531 minimizing the residual sum of squares (RSS):

532

$$RSS = \|X - \alpha Z^T\|_2$$

533

534 Here, α represents the coefficients of the archetypes in an $n \times k$ matrix. The elements of
535 α are non-negative and their sum must be 1, i.e., $\sum_{j=1}^k \alpha_{ij} = 1$ with $\alpha_{ij} \geq 0$ for $i =$
536 $1, \dots, n$. Additionally, the archetypes Z are themselves convex combinations of the data
537 points:

538

$$Z = X^T \beta$$

539

540 where β is an $n \times k$ matrix of coefficients. The elements of β are also non-negative and
541 their sum must be 1, i.e., $\sum_{i=1}^n \beta_{ji} = 1$ with $\beta_{ji} \geq 0$ for $j = 1, \dots, k$. Each archetype
542 represents an extreme observation of the dataset, and the remaining observations are
543 interpreted based on their proximity to these archetypes (Eugster and Leisch 2009;
544 Eugster and Leisch 2011).

545

544 **Profiling humanist archetypes**

545 To identify transversal profiles across the archetypes derived from 13 fields, we
546 employed an unsupervised clustering approach. First, the archetype values, expressed
547 as percentiles, were normalized to ensure comparability across different attributes. This
548 normalization adjusted the data so that all attributes, regardless of their original scale,
549 contributed equally to the clustering process. We then applied a hierarchical clustering
550 algorithm, visualized through a clustered heatmap generated using the pheatmap library
551 in R (Kolde 2025). The clustering was based on Euclidean distance, which measures the
552 dissimilarity between archetypes by calculating the geometric distance between their

553 attribute vectors. By grouping archetypes that exhibited similar patterns across the
554 attributes, this method uncovered latent structural relationships between archetypes
555 from different fields.

556

557 To determine the optimal number of clusters, we tested various configurations,
558 systematically evaluating the interpretability and coherence of the resulting groupings.
559 Ultimately, a six-cluster solution was chosen as the most suitable. Based on the common
560 patterns identified within each cluster, the profiles were labeled to clearly reflect their
561 distinctive characteristics.

562

563 **Keyword extraction**

564 Publications were limited to those in Spanish and English language, that 85.79% of the
565 analyzed dataset (708,355 records). To ensure an accurate analysis, all publication titles
566 were first translated into English using the ChatGPT API (GPT-4) (OpenAI 2022).
567 Keywords were then extracted from the document titles using the Rapid Keyword
568 Extraction (RAKE) algorithm (Rose et al. 2010). RAKE is an unsupervised, domain-
569 independent method that extracts keywords by analyzing the frequency and co-
570 occurrence of words within a text. The process begins with text segmentation, where the
571 input text is divided into candidate keywords by removing stop words and punctuation.
572 Each candidate keyword is then scored based on its frequency and degree of co-
573 occurrence with other words. The degree is defined as the number of co-occurrences of
574 word with all other words within candidate keywords.

575

576 The scoring mechanism of RAKE can be expressed mathematically as follows: for a
577 candidate keyword k , the score $S(k)$ is calculated as:

578

$$S(k) = \sum_{w \in k} \frac{deg(w)}{freq(w)}$$

579

580 Where $freq(w)$ is the frequency of word w in the text, and $deg(w)$ is the degree of word
581 w , which is the sum of all co-occurrences of that word with other words within candidate
582 keywords. The algorithm's final output is a ranked list of keywords, with higher scoring
583 keywords deemed more relevant.

583

584 **Creation of thematic landscapes and topic detection**

585 We then generated a document-keyword matrix from which we extracted a term co-
586 mention network generated based on the publications of each author, applying a binary
587 counting method. This means that the co-occurrence of terms across all papers by the
588 same author was considered, but only in terms of whether the keyword was present or
589 not, ignoring the frequency. As a result, a co-occurrence network was obtained,
590 calculating the weight between keywords as the frequency of their appearance in distinct
591 authors. However, we normalized the weights to avoid problems when clustering due to
592 the presence of terms with high frequency. The normalized weight w_{norm} is calculated
593 as follows:

594

$$w_{norm} = \frac{2 \times w}{f_x + f_y}$$

595

596 where w is the original weight, and f_x and f_y are the total occurrence frequencies of
individual terms x and y . This normalization considers the total frequency of term across

597 all authors versus their co-occurrence with each other, helping to balance the weights
598 and reduce the impact of highly frequent terms in the clustering process.

599

600 The resulting network was filtered to include only terms that co-occur at least twice. Using
601 the Leiden community detection algorithm (Traag et al. 2019), clusters were identified,
602 resulting in a total of 4,829 clusters ($Q = 0.825$), representing thematic clusters that
603 correspond to research topics. However, since many clusters were composed of only a
604 few terms, we further filtered to include only clusters with more than four terms, reducing
605 the total to 1,452 topics. Following this, the co-occurrence network was aggregated by
606 summing the normalized weights w_{norm} within each topic, resulting in a network of 1,437
607 nodes, representing the thematic landscape of the humanities. This network
608 encompasses the keywords from 676,489 publications (81.5% of total publications). We
609 then use VOSviewer to visualize the network and apply the Leiden community detection
610 algorithm to further cluster topics into 8 major fields. From the general map, an overlay
611 was created for each archetype within each discipline, showcasing the research fronts
612 where they publish the most.

613

614 **Thematic profile similarity**

615 Finally, we represented each humanist profile as a vector, where each entry corresponds
616 to the total number of publications in a specific research topic. Pairwise distances
617 between these topic vectors were then computed using the Jaccard distance, which
618 quantifies dissimilarity by comparing shared and unique topics between profiles. The
619 Jaccard distance d_j between two sets A and B is defined as:

620

$$d_j(A, B) = 1 - \frac{|A \cap B|}{|A \cup B|}$$

621 where $|A \cap B|$ is the size of the intersection (i.e., the number of shared topics) and $|A \cup$
622 $B|$ is the size of the union (i.e., the total number of unique topics across both profiles).
623 Subsequently, we applied Multidimensional Scaling (MDS) with a two-dimensional
624 solution (Davison and Sireci 2000) analysis to visualize how profiles align based on
625 thematic similarity. This analysis allowed us to assess whether the observed thematic
626 patterns at the field level were consistent across the broader dataset.

627

628 **Endnotes**

629 ¹<https://dialnet.unirioja.es/>

630 ²<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13905465>

631 ³https://github.com/Wences91/humanities_patterns

632

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800

801

802 **Competing interests**

803 The authors declare no competing interests.

804

805 **Data availability**

806 Data underlying this study and supplementary materials are available at
807 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13905465>. Code scripts are available at the GitHub
808 repository https://github.com/Wences91/humanities_patterns.

809

810 **Ethical approval**

811 Ethical approval was not required as this study did not involve human participants or
812 animal subjects.

813

814 **Informed consent**

815 This article does not contain any studies with human participants performed by any of
816 the authors.

817

818 **Figures**

819 Fig. 1 Descriptives of population of scholars and outputs by field. (a) Distribution of
820 scholars by research field and (b) publications. (c) Boxplot of academic ages by field.
821 Career length refers to the difference between their first and last years of publication. (d)
822 Boxplot of the distribution of first year of publication by field. This is used to describe
823 generational differences among scholars. (e) Distribution of publications by publication
824 type and field. (f) Distribution of publication by language and field. Data filtered to
825 scholars with publications since 1950 and with more than one publication and include all
826 publication types.

827

828 Fig. 2 Clustering of archetypes in the humanities. (a) Description and characterization of
829 the six clusters of archetypes identified for the complete population of scholars. Rows
830 show the parameters associated with each archetype, with labels on the right side of the
831 heatmap indicating the discipline and a number which corresponds with each of the
832 archetypes identified within the discipline. Rows are grouped based on a hierarchical
833 clustering with labels on the left side indicating the name of the cluster. Values are
834 normalized 0-1 based on the proportion of output expected by scholars based on the
835 eight variables (columns) analyzed. These values represent the extent to which an
836 archetype's scholarly output is distributed across specific categories. Consequently,
837 when summing categories that are mutually exclusive (such as Articles, Books,
838 Chapters, Confeditor, Editor, and Proceedings), the total equals 1, reflecting the
839 complete distribution of scholarly output across these dimensions. (b) Multidimensional
840 Scaling (MDS) plot providing a spatial representation of the relational distances between
841 archetypes and disciplines. The configuration highlights patterns of proximity and
842 divergence in archetypal profiles, allowing for the visualization of disciplinary clustering
843 and the structural similarity among publication behaviors.

844

845 Fig. 3 Generational shifts in publication profiles across disciplines. Stacked bar charts by
846 discipline on the distribution of scholars based on their first publication year. The color of
847 the segments within each bar corresponds to the publication profiles identified in Fig. 2
848 to facilitate comparisons within and across fields.

849

850 Fig. 4 Thematic landscape and comparison of research portfolios by archetype in History,
851 Philology, Philosophy and Arts. Top-left shows the base thematic map based on a co-
852 occurrence matrix of keywords extracted from titles for the complete population. The right
853 side includes the research portfolio of scholars in each discipline by publication profile.
854

855 Fig. 5 Thematic similarity of profiles across academic fields. (a) Multidimensional Scaling
856 (MDS) representation in two dimensions showing the relative thematic similarity of
857 scholarly profiles across all academic fields. Each point corresponds to a profile,
858 positioned in a continuous spatial configuration based on thematic proximity. Shorter
859 distances between points indicate greater thematic similarity in the content of scholarly
860 output. (b) The same MDS projection, with selective highlighting by academic field. Each
861 panel emphasizes the profiles belonging to one specific field, while maintaining the global
862 spatial layout.
863